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D4.2 Data Plagiarism Checker Results

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Abbreviations

CSV	Comma Separated Value
RDBMS	Relational Database Management Systems
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
XML	Extensible Markup Language
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
NoSQL	Non-relational databases
FAISS	Facebook AI Similarity Search

Executive summary

Dataset plagiarism is a growing concern in the research community. It is crucial to prevent researchers from uploading or generating slightly modified resource updates and asserting ownership or authorship of research outputs without making a substantial contribution. This report aims to investigate various plagiarism detection methods specifically tailored to common research dataset formats, such as images, time series, and comma-separated values (csv). The result of this work will be used as a module for the RAISE EU project's distributed crowdsourced data processing system. First, we explore transformer models for image plagiarism detection. Second, we adapt the SFA representation to detect plagiarism in time-series. Finally, we explore cosine similarity, Jaccard index, Earth Mover's Distance and Cramer's V to detect plagiarism in csv datasets. We have evaluated our methods using publicly available datasets as well as datasets generated by RAISE.

1 Introduction

In recent years, alongside improvements in computing power, the need for processing large amounts of information, i.e., the Big Data concept, arose rapidly in various scientific domains. As a result, the amount of data generated has increased dramatically [1]. Data can be **structured**, **semi-structured**, or **unstructured**.

1.1 Types of data in the RAISE Project

Structured data (also called 'tabular') are presented in table format, arranged into rows and columns. The columns represent the names of each variable (or object), and the rows represent the corresponding records or observations for each variable. The type of those data can be Text, Date, Numerical, or Categorical. Numerical data can be continuous or discrete, while categorical data can be nominal or ordinal. Structured data are usually stored in files such as text (txt), comma-separated values (CSV), or in relational database management systems (RDBMS). The second data schema is **semi-structured** data, which, instead of the tabular format, usually consists of pairs of keys and values. Semi-structured data is stored either in JSON (JavaScript Object Notation), XML (Extensible Markup Language), or HTML files. The third data schema is **unstructured data**, which concerns either image files, text files, audio files, or video files. These make up a strong majority of the world's generated data. Unstructured data is stored either in non-relational NoSQL databases, Object-based storage, Data Lakes, or on Big Data Platforms.[2]

1.2 Open-source data and plagiarism

At the same time, the sources from which anyone can find the available data have also increased. Some of the data is open, meaning that no permission is required for personal use. In this way, anyone can reuse them without the knowledge of their creator. Of course, all online content is subject to the applicable copyright licenses (like Creative Commons licences). Using data without relevant permission is considered data plagiarism.

The AHA's Statement on Standards of Professional Conduct defines plagiarism as the appropriation of the exact wording of another author without attribution, and the borrowing of distinctive and significant research findings or interpretations without proper citation [3]. On the other side, data plagiarism is a significant issue for data repositories. Malicious authors can create datasets that closely resemble those already in the repository and claim them as their own.

Plagiarism detection tools have been available for many years [4]. Recently, some platforms have started using Machine Learning algorithms to detect plagiarism. Machine Learning (ML) is a field of Artificial Intelligence that uses analytical methods to extract information from data (data mining), without necessarily human intervention.

In recent years, several algorithms have been developed to detect plagiarism in text [5,6]. Additionally, there are methods that can successfully recognize similarities between two different files [7]. The aim of this work is to identify suitable algorithms for detecting plagiarism between two datasets. To the best of our knowledge, the use of ML methodologies in data plagiarism apart from text has not been extensively performed. Thus, the purpose of this paper was to expand and explore the appropriate statistical and machine learning algorithms for detecting plagiarism in structured and unstructured data, under various scenarios. The examined datasets are images, time-series, and comma-separated value (csv) files.

2 Literature Review

While plagiarism detection in text data has concerned the scientific community for many years, limited work has been conducted for other types of data, such as images or tabular data.

The Vision Transformer was proposed in [8] and it was the first paper that successfully trained a transformer encoder on ImageNet [23], achieving very good results in comparison to familiar convolutional architectures. Some other works based on Visual Transformer were released after that. DeiT models [9] by Microsoft research are distilled vision transformers. The authors propose

strategies to train image transformer models effectively even when the available labelled data is limited and explore knowledge distillation through attention mechanisms. DINO [10] is a self-supervised training framework for vision transformers by Facebook AI, which shows very interesting properties not seen with convolutional models. The models using DINO are capable of segmenting objects, without having trained on this task using self-supervised learning.

P. Hurtik et al. created a framework for image plagiarism detection, FTIP [12], which applies a transformation to images to search for plagiarized images in a database. The authors used their own images and tested their approach by cropping or adding noise to their original images. K. Gayadhankar et al. proposed an image plagiarism detection approach using a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [16]. The process begins with the upload of an image. Following this, the image undergoes pre-processing and feature extraction, where both local and global features are extracted. Subsequently, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithm is applied. This CNN algorithm is trained using a GAN-generated or fake image dataset. The purpose of this algorithm is to determine whether the uploaded image is artificially generated by a GAN or if it is genuine. The results of this determination are then displayed on a website. Notably, the fake image dataset used for training the algorithm comprises images of size 8x8, resulting in a total of 64 images. This size choice aims to offer users a variety of image options for selection. It considers that GANs, along with producing replicas, also introduce some noise in the output during image generation. By generating images in the 8x8 format, the replicas can be better distinguished from the noise in the final output. However, this method is costly in terms of time and resources due to the training of the networks.

The Earth Mover's Distance (EMD) is a method to evaluate dissimilarity between two multi-dimensional distributions in some feature space where a distance measure between single features, which we call the ground distance is given. In general, it is suitable as a metric for image retrieval but in the present work it was used to compare the categorical variables before and after the presence of noise. This technique was shown to work more efficiently than classical similarity metrics such as cosine similarity and Jaccard index [14, 15].

In [20] the authors compare five distance measures for plagiarism detection in music files. More specifically the authors tried the following three cases: a pair of plagiarized songs, a pair of same song with different lengths, and a random pair of songs. Their results show that DTW performed best for all the test-cases. Music plagiarism detection is close to time series plagiarism because a song can be viewed as a special case of time series.

3 Methods

As a first approach we tried using sddhash[19] as a data plagiarism detection method on structured data. Sddhash is a file fingerprinting utility. We applied sddhash on CSV files. Sddhash worked well for row additions, row deletions, rows shuffling and columns addition while it failed in noise addition, columns deletion and column shuffling. A repository for the sddhash utility for data plagiarism is available at: (https://repo.raise-science.eu/raise_dev/rai-certified-node/plagiarism-checker-standalone/). We then explored methods on unstructured (images), semi-structured (time-series). For the final implementation, we have developed algorithms that are accessible on GitHub.: [GitHub - aglenis/raise_data_plagiarism](https://github.com/aglenis/raise_data_plagiarism).

The results are reproducible by using the datasets:

The modified UCR datasets are in the following link : <https://zenodo.org/records/10609432>

The original UCR datasets can be found at: <http://www.timeseriesclassification.com/dataset.php>

The vicomtech dataset can be found at:

https://github.com/aglenis/raise_data_plagiarism/tree/main/data

The noisy datasets for the CSV plagiarism use-case are in the following link:<https://zenodo.org/records/10619035>

The imaging dataset can be found at: <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vqg/data/oxbuildings/>

3.1 CSV Plagiarism Investigation

CSV (Comma-Separated Values) files are used to store tabular data with numerical or categorical variables, where each row represents a record. For our experiments, we used 4 datasets which are publicly available and contain both categorical and numerical variables with different row and column sizes. [Table 2].

For the model evaluation, we address three scenarios. In the first scenario, noise was introduced to the numerical variables from a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation equal to the percentage of the dataset. For example, if a standard deviation of 10% is selected, the function will compute the column's standard deviation and then take 10% of that value.

Another function utilized the cosine similarity distance metric to extract the percentage of similarity between numerical variables, while the Jaccard index is used to extract the percentage of similarity between categorical variables. If the dataset includes both numerical and categorical data, the plagiarism score is calculated as the average of the cosine similarity and Jaccard similarity metrics: $(\text{cosine_score} + \text{jaccard_score}) / 2$. The score ranges from 0 to 1, with a higher score indicating a greater similarity, i.e. plagiarism.

The function mentioned above is not affected by variable names or missing values. However, there are cases where comparing two files can lead to complications. These scenarios arise when rows have been either added or deleted.

The second scenario involves adding rows, but in practice, this doesn't imply adding rows from the existing. Instead, a percentage of new rows with different values is added. To illustrate this let's consider a situation where a researcher has conducted an identical study to someone else, and the latter enriches their data with the former's data. This is a classic example of plagiarism. The function we created simulates a percentage of rows with values that follow the distribution of the existing ones. To make the difference noticeable we used percentages of 10%, 30%, and 60%.

A normal distribution was assumed for the quantitative variables, with the mean and variance of the corresponding column of the data set. For the categorical variables, we were based on the frequency distribution of the categories in each column. Cosine similarity and the Jaccard Index were not used for comparison as it would not be meaningful, since it would result in comparing the original dataset with a significant percentage of itself. This results in values that are consistently close to 1. To achieve more accurate comparisons, we need to use more advanced methods that consider factors beyond the data's structure and distribution. These are Earth Mover's Distance for numerical columns and Cramér's V for categorical columns.

In the third scenario, a percentage of random rows are removed from each column in the dataset. The optimal method for this case is still Earth Mover's Distance for numerical columns and Cramér's V for categorical columns.

Name of dataset	Number of Rows	Number of columns
KI	80	18
Iris ¹	150	5
PIMA ²	768	9
Titanic ³	891	8

Table 1: Datasets description

¹ <https://data.world/uci/iris>

² <https://data.world/data-society/pima-indians-diabetes-database>

³ <https://data.world/nrippner/titanic-disaster-dataset>

3.2 Time-series Plagiarism Investigation

Time series datasets are difficult to manage since changes in the columns or noise can alter the key characteristics of a time series and thus allow the plagiarised time series to become undetectable. To address this problem, we need to represent the time series in a manner that is resilient to noise and can also account for differences in columns. To this end we have chosen to transform the time series using SFA [11]. SFA is a text representation resilient to noise.

More specifically our method works as follows:

In the first step each time series in the dataset is converted to its SFA representation, then for each time series we create a Term Frequency Vector from the SFA representation. In the third step we take the Mean of all the Term Frequency Vectors in the dataset to create a single embedding for the dataset. Finally, to measure the similarity of two datasets we take the cosine similarity of two embeddings.

For the dataset we used the parking space dataset provided by Vicomtech⁴. The parking space dataset contains the free parking spaces over time for 16 parking locations. For each parking location we have 10 measurements resulting in a 16*10 time series dataset.

For our evaluation on the time series datasets, we used the training set of eight datasets from the UCR Time Series Repository [10]. Below we describe the Time Series Datasets:

Name	Number of samples	Number of classes	Number of timestamps
Crop	7200	24	46
FordB	3636	2	500
FordA	3601	2	500
NonInvasiveFetalEC GThorax2	1800	42	750
NonInvasiveFetalEC GThorax1	1800	42	750
PhalangesOutlinesCo rrect	1800	2	80
HandOutlines	1000	2	2709
TwoPatterns	1000	4	128

Table 2: UCR datasets description

For our evaluation we address the following scenarios:

1. **Adding Noise:** For noise addition we generated noise from a normal distribution with standard deviation equal to the percentage of the dataset.
2. **Adding Rows:** For rows addition we took a percentage of random rows indexes and added them to the end of the dataset.
3. **Removing Rows:** For columns deletions we took a percentage of random rows indexes and removed them from the dataset.
4. **Adding Columns:** For columns addition we took a percentage of random column indexes and added them to the end of the dataset.

⁴ <https://www.vicomtech.org/en/>

5. **Removing Columns:** For columns deletions we took a percentage of random columns indexes and removed them from the dataset. For the percentages we tried 10%,20% and 30%.

3.3 Image Plagiarism Investigation

In this investigation, pre-trained transformer models were employed to detect image plagiarism (unstructured data). To the best of our understanding, this study represents a pioneering effort in utilizing pre-trained transformer models specifically tailored for the task of image plagiarism detection. Remarkably, these models exhibited exceptional performance, showcasing their efficacy without the need for resource-intensive training procedures.

For our experiments, we used the Oxford dataset⁵ which is publicly available and contains 5062 images sourced from Flickr. The dataset underwent manual annotation to generate a comprehensive ground truth for 11 distinct landmarks, each associated with five potential queries. Notably, within this dataset, there are divergent perspectives of the same landmark, rendering the collection particularly intricate for tasks involving image plagiarism detection.

For each image in the query files, three distinct categories have been established. The "good" category designates images that closely resemble the query image. The "ok" category encompasses images that bear some similarity to the query image. Lastly, the "bad" category includes images that are unrelated to the query images. For the purposes of evaluation of our approaches we gave the label 1 to the images of categories "good" and "ok" and 0 to "bad".

4 Results

4.1 CSV Plagiarism Investigation

The algorithm performs well in both cases when noise is added to the numerical and categorical variables, as shown in Tables from 13 to 15. The cosine similarity starts at 0.95 for noise addition and reaches 0.77 for 30% of noise. For row addition, the cosine similarity starts at 0.98 for 10% of noise and reaches 0.75 for 60% of noise.

However, when rows are removed, the algorithm still works correctly but produces very low results, as demonstrated in Table 17. The Earth Mover's distance was used to compare the distributions of each numerical column in the original and modified datasets, as well as the Cramer's V Score to compare the frequency distributions of each categorical column. The results were similar, indicating that these methods are more sensitive to changes in the case of row removal.

In conclusion, the algorithm works well with noise input. It is easy to identify a threshold for plagiarism. However, when lines are added or removed, there is no clear threshold. This is because the plagiarism rate depends on the sample size, as well as the percentage of quantitative and qualitative variables in the data. The results were not interpretable due to the addition and removal of columns from the data. CSV files are complex by nature, as many factors can affect the results.

Noise to numerical features	Noise to categorical features		
	10%	20%	30%
10%	0.904	0.897	0.885
20%	0.832	0.825	0.813
30%	0.787	0.779	0.767

⁵ <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/data/oxbuildings/>

Table 3: : Result of CSV Plagiarism Investigation of KI dataset under various scenarios of noise percentage introduced.

Noise to numerical features	Noise to categorical features		
	10%	20%	30%
10%	0.954	0.901	0.851
20%	0.940	0.887	0.837
30%	0.919	0.866	0.816

Table 4: Result of CSV Plagiarism Investigation of Iris dataset under various scenarios of noise percentage introduced.

Noise to numerical features	Noise to categorical features		
	10%	20%	30%
10%	0.930	0.862	0.806
20%	0.920	0.852	0.797
30%	0.905	0.837	0.781

Table 5: Result of CSV Plagiarism Investigation of Titanic dataset under various scenarios of noise percentage introduced.

Name of dataset	10%	30%	60%
KI	0.828	0.789	0.760
Iris	0.981	0.968	0.959
Pima	0.858	0.792	0.757
Titanic	0.956	0.923	0.895

Table 6: Result of CSV Plagiarism Investigation of different datasets under various scenarios of row addition percentage introduced.

Name of dataset	10%	30%	60%
KI	0.441	0.361	0.265
Iris	0.895	0.651	0.600
Pima	0.372	0.329	0.267
Titanic	0.476	0.451	0.426

Table 7: Result of CSV Plagiarism Investigation of different datasets under various scenarios of row removing percentage introduced.

In conclusion, the algorithm works well in the presence of noise. However, it is more sensitive when rows are removed or added. CSV files have more parameters than other files because they not only depend on the sample size but also on the percentage of qualitative variables present in them.

4.2 Time series Plagiarism Investigation

In our test we compare the input time-series with the plagiarised after both have been transformed using SFA. We expect that plagiarised time series with higher percentage of rows/columns addition/deletions will have lower cosine similarity. Here the perfect score is 1.0 and values closer to that indicate that there is a high probability that plagiarism has occurred. As we can see using SFA works well both for removing noise and column transformation.

For noise addition, the cosine similarity starts at 0.89 and reaches 0.85 for 30% of noise. This means that the algorithm can effectively disregard the noise added to the dataset (Table 4).

For appending rows, the cosine similarity is above 0.99 for all configurations. Similarly for deleting rows the cosine similarity is above 0.99 for all configurations (Tables 5-12). This means that the algorithm is robust when we manipulate rows. When manipulating columns, we can see that when we add columns the cosine similarity is always above 0.98. When deleting columns, the cosine similarity is always above 0.99. This means that the algorithm behaves well both when adding and deleting columns.

Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.8914	0.9973	0.9959	0.9967	0.9966
20%	0.8598	0.9957	0.9884	0.9893	0.9932
30%	0.8548	0.9971	0.9909	0.9849	0.9956

Table 8: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the Vicomtech dataset

Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.9954	0.9999	0.9999	0.9990	0.9993
20%	0.9797	0.9999	0.9999	0.9975	0.9945
30%	0.9447	0.9999	0.9999	0.9970	0.9877

Table 9: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the Crop dataset

Percent	Method
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	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.9995	0.9999	0.9999	0.9989	0.9962
20%	0.9950	0.9999	0.9999	0.9961	0.9799
30%	0.9837	0.9999	0.9999	0.9920	0.9447

Table 10: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the FordA dataset

Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.9997	0.9999	0.9999	0.9988	0.9941
20%	0.9964	0.9999	0.9999	0.9959	0.9699
30%	0.9869	0.9999	0.9999	0.9915	0.9152

Table 11: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the FordB dataset

Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.8116	0.9999	0.9999	0.9996	0.9999
20%	0.7070	0.9999	0.9999	0.9986	0.9998
30%	0.6335	0.9999	0.9999	0.9968	0.9992

Table 12: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the Hand Outlines dataset

Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.9553	0.9999	0.9999	0.9965	0.9990
20%	0.9103	0.9999	0.9999	0.9942	0.9964
30%	0.8698	0.9999	0.9999	0.9887	0.9915

Table 13: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the NonInvasiveFetalECGThorax1 dataset

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Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.9326	0.9999	0.9999	0.9973	0.9992
20%	0.8762	0.9999	0.9999	0.9950	0.9971
30%	0.8329	0.9999	0.9999	0.9906	0.9932

Table 14: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the NonInvasiveFetalECGThorax2 dataset

Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.9326	0.9999	0.9999	0.9973	0.9992
20%	0.8762	0.9999	0.9999	0.9950	0.9971
30%	0.8329	0.9999	0.9999	0.9906	0.9932

Table 15: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the NonInvasiveFetalECGThorax2 dataset

Percent	Method				
	Noise	Row append	Row delete	Column append	Column delete
10%	0.9244	0.9999	0.9999	0.9981	0.9890
20%	0.9116	0.9999	0.9999	0.9937	0.9626
30%	0.9028	0.9999	0.9998	0.9849	0.9438

Table 16: Results of Time Series Plagiarism Investigation for the TwoPatterns dataset

4.3 Image plagiarism investigation

Our approach was to create a system that given a query image and a collection of images, would be able to identify if the query image is relevant (plagiarized) to any of the images in the collection. In our attempt to make this system efficient and avoid pairwise comparison (or classification) between images, we transformed every image in a fixed size vector (representation) using visual transformers and stored it in a vector database. Following this approach, given a query image, we vectorize it by using the transformer and apply cosine similarities between the query embedding and the embeddings in our database. Note that this operation is very efficient for vector databases (such as

ChromaDB⁶ and FAISS⁷). This approach was inspired by the way Semantic Search Engines works for text similarity.

All the vision transformers used during this research were image classification models. To extract the embeddings of every image, we used the last hidden layer of the network. The last hidden layer of a trained network contains all the information regarding the representation of the input since the output layer usually employs just an activation function suitable for the task at hand. Note that since we used pretrained transformers there is no need for training or recalculation every time a new image is inserted to the collection.

We conducted a comparative analysis between three types of Visual Transformer: the classic Visual Transformer, the Visual Transformer trained under DINO⁸ and DINOv2⁹ frameworks. All the pretrained models are accessible through the ‘hugging face’ python library. The models were trained on ImageNet 1k dataset (<https://image-net.org/index.php>). We approached this comparison as a classification task, aiming to categorize a given query image into either plagiarized or non-plagiarized classes. We also consider different thresholds for the cosine similarity. Since the dataset is imbalanced concerning the labels, we report the F1-metric. In Table 1 we present the average of F1-score from the 55 queries of the Oxford dataset for different cosine similarity thresholds.

	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
ViT	0.836	0.853	0.85	0.797	0.626	0.364	0.145
DINO	0.834	0.849	0.843	0.807	0.7	0.5	0.204
DINO v2	0.828	0.845	0.871	0.86	0.758	0.607	0.322

Table 17: Results of F1 – score from the 55 queries of the Oxford dataset for different cosine similarity thresholds

5 Conclusions and future work

In this study, we have explored and implemented innovative approaches for plagiarism detection across diverse data types, including structured (CSV), time series, and unstructured (images) data. Our findings and methodologies shed light on the challenges and opportunities inherent in each domain. For structured data, our algorithm demonstrated commendable performance in detecting plagiarism when noise was added to both numerical and categorical variables. However, the interpretability of results diminished when rows were added or removed, emphasizing the complexity introduced by various factors such as sample size and variable percentages. In the realm of time series data, the utilization of Symbolic Fourier Approximation (SFA) proved to be a robust strategy. The algorithm exhibited resilience in scenarios involving noise addition, rows/columns addition/deletions, showcasing its effectiveness in detecting temporal plagiarism. SFA's ability to handle transformations while maintaining high cosine similarity scores highlights its potential for widespread adoption in time series plagiarism detection. The image plagiarism investigation presented a pioneering system that efficiently leverages visual transformers and vector databases for similarity assessment. The comparative analysis of different transformers—classic Visual Transformer, DINO, and DINOv2—provided insights into their classification performance. The system's reliance on cosine similarity and F1-metric evaluation demonstrated its efficacy, offering a promising approach for scalable and accurate image plagiarism detection.

⁶ <https://www.trychroma.com/>

⁷ <https://engineering.fb.com/2017/03/29/data-infrastructure/faiss-a-library-for-efficient-similarity-search/>

⁸ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/dino>

⁹ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/dinov2>

It is important to be mentioned here that plagiarism detection in data other than text is an untapped area from the scientific community. The papers that are referenced in the Literature Review section, use their own datasets without making them public and in most of the situations the source code is not available. As a result, to the best of our knowledge, there is not an established benchmark dataset for the researchers to compare their algorithms. The work presented in this paper provides the source and the noisy datasets which could be an approach towards creating a benchmark dataset to be used by the research community.

Future work on the challenges presented in this paper include the utilization of transformers to extract a semantic representation of an image, and then use Large Language Models to compute the embeddings and find similarities between images. A variety of approaches could be investigated for the cases of similarity in CSV files, simulating various scenarios and using Large Language Models (LLMs) to extract robust results. Accuracy (i.e. repeatability) of the results in both research and clinical practice is a cornerstone in research methodology to make robust conclusions about the tested hypothesis on datasets. LLMs and deep machine learning techniques in general could find patterns more efficiently than any other technique. When it is about time series plagiarism detection, future work should focus on using more complex representations for the embeddings possibly using Transformer architectures [21,22].

Finally, part of the future work in RAISE is the development of adaptive thresholding mechanisms based on data characteristics and sample size to address the challenges observed in structured data, specifically when rows are added or removed. In addition, RAISE will further refine of time series plagiarism detection techniques by investigating advanced approaches beyond SFA that can accommodate even more intricate temporal variations. In addition, the work presented in TabTransformer [17] and FT-Transformer [18], which are proven to have great performance on predictive tasks in comparison with classic ML algorithms, will be investigated further and applied in our case.

Some limitation and challenges in the domain are that the models and algorithms presented are trained and evaluated on specific datasets and even specific types of datasets, while the computational intensity of certain algorithms, especially those involving deep learning and transformer models, may limit their applicability in resource-constrained environments.

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